

INTRINSIC JOINING OF INCOMPATIBLE FIBER-REINFORCED PLASTICS BY PHOTONICS

S. Schmitt, R. Schares, M. Emonts, K. Fischer

Aachen Center for Integrative Lightweight Production, RWTH Aachen University
Steinbachstr. 19, D-52074 Aachen, Germany

Email: Stefan.Schmitt@azl.rwth-aachen.de, web page: <http://www.azl.rwth-aachen.de>

Keywords: Back-molding, Integrated production cell, Intrinsic joining, Laser processing, RTM

ABSTRACT

To preserve resources and to reduce the exhaust of CO₂ by using the full lightweight potential of thermoset and thermoplastic fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP), a large-scale suitable manufacturing of these incompatible materials is essential. A promising approach is an intrinsic joining by back-molding, enabled by photonics. Key production step of the new process technology is an interposed laser machining process, in which the joining zone of a thermoset carbon fiber-reinforced RTM part will be treated by selective material removal. This represents the basis for an effectual intrinsic joining and internal load transmission by micro clamping of the exposed continuous fibers.

The objective of the project "OPTO-Light" (funding ref. no. 13N12696) funded by the German Ministry of Education and Research is to use the synergy of continuous fiber-reinforced thermosets and fiber-reinforced thermoplastics to manufacture structural lightweight parts with high mechanical load capacity, low tendency to creep and high functional integrity, enabled by photonic processes. This will be achieved the first time in one fully integrated close-to-series-production cell, including controlled laser and optical quality assurance systems.

Beside the selection of the essential process methodology and system technology of RTM and injection molding, the novel process chain has been proven. Influences of the fiber architectures and the injection molding process were investigated. The investigations by the use of a pulsed laser with continuous carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy systems and a short glass fiber-reinforced polyamide 6 result in shear strengths above 14 MPa.

Figure 1: In the front: Continuous fiber-reinforced thermoset with locally exposed fibers at the joining zone. In the back: Hybrid sample with back-molded short fiber-reinforced thermoplastic

1 INTRODUCTION

Up to now, the manufacturing of lightweight parts, made of continuous fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP) is a compromise about possible freedom of design (e.g. ribs and shaped elements), material selection (e.g. fiber length and mechanical properties) and cost effectiveness (e.g. cycle time and number of process steps).

1.1 Established material systems

The example of the BMW i3 lifemodule shows, for structural parts the industry mainly prefers thermoset continuous fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP) due to their high mechanical strength and stiffness by coexisting low tendency to creep. Nevertheless for geometrical complex designs, the use of continuous FRP is constricted and the realization of e.g. ribs for additional design stiffness and further benefit in lightweight performance can be only achieved by complex and costly 3d-preforming processes, which are difficult to implement in large-scale productions. The choice to use thermoset materials furthermore is been backed by the possibility to use load optimized fiber structures, fast curing epoxy systems, high reactive polyurethanes and the implementation of advanced Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) technologies like High Pressure RTM and Gap Impregnation.

Besides thermoset resins, thermoplastic FRP parts are increasingly being applied in the automotive industry. This is due to the easy processing by using pre-impregnated sheets and the possibility to functionalize the parts by back-molding with short fiber-reinforced thermoplastics. Due to the reversible meltability of thermoplastics, adhesive bonding mechanisms lead to a good bonding between the continuous fiber-reinforced substrate and the molding compound. Major disadvantages of thermoplastics are their tendency to creep and the limited lightweight potential due to the pre-defined fiber orientations within the prepregs.

1.2 Joining of thermoset and thermoplastic FRP

The joining of thermoset and thermoplastic materials is an essential aspect, due to its incompatibility for basic joining technologies like welding. Thus approaches are predominantly adhesive bonding and primary shaping. [1]

But the classical joining by adhesive bonding or macro-scale form closure can be substituted by an integral approach [2]. In this approach, the fiber structure will be kept intact and no additional weights like joining elements or adhesives will be inserted, to shorten the process chain. An example to realize a surface bonding and to functionalize afterwards is the application of dissolvable thermoplastics on the mold just before the impregnation of the preform and before the curing of the thermoset [3]. Amongst others, this kind of joining technology is known as „Thermoset Composite Welding (TCW)“ and used in the aircraft industry by the company ACS, Port Melbourne, Australia. Additionally the joining of thermoset FRP by vibration joining with the application of a thin thermoplastic film was investigated [4]. To join thermoset and thermoplastic FRP with the laser-based hot-melt bonding, the welding process is done after a photonic treatment of the surface [5]. But the need of this technology for transparent and preformed thermoplastic parts reduces the usable materials and the freedom of design.

2 THE “OPTO-LIGHT” PROCESS CHAIN

Together with the project partners ARGES GmbH, Wackersdorf, BMW AG, München, KraussMaffei Technologies GmbH, München, Precitec GmbH & Co.KG, Gaggenau, Sensortherm GmbH, Sulzbach, and Steinbichler Optotechnik GmbH. Neubeuern, the objective of the project “OPTO-Light” is to manufacture functionalized lightweight parts of continuous fiber-reinforced thermosets with short fiber-reinforced thermoplastics in a single integrative production cell, enabled for close-to-series production by using photonic technologies. The project is funded by the German Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF).

The novel process chain mainly consists of three steps: RTM, laser treatment, injection molding. Included is also a quality assurance by a 3d laser scanning system. To achieve a sufficient bonding strength, a microform closure is achieved by an interposed laser machining process to expose the continuous fibers using precise and powerful laser radiation. This laser treatment and selective material removal of the joining zone of a thermoset carbon fiber-reinforced RTM part is the key process step and represents the basis for an effective intrinsic joining by back-molding. The main process steps are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Novel "OPTO-Light" main process steps for the manufacturing of hybrid parts, made of FRP multi-material systems, enabled by photonic processes

The entire curing of the thermoset material prevents a following material-logical reaction with a thermoplastic. So the laser process is used for the automated pre-treatment of complex 3d joining surfaces. In general this pre-treatment offers a high potential to increase the strength of the bonding area, due to a concurrent cleaning, warming and further physical bonding effects. The laser processing offers advantages compared to mechanical or chemical pre-treatments, due to the fast and defined beam guidance. Particularly to the requirement to prepare small circular or long joining surfaces for fixings and stiffening ribs. In general the exposure of the fiber structure can be used as a pre-treatment process for a variety of joining processes in which a microform-fit (facilitated by superficial sublimation of the matrix material without damaging the surrounding fibers and fiber wetting by another medium) can contribute to improved performance and efficiency.

Furthermore the OPTO-Light process admits of cost savings in the production. By the substitution of a usual multi-stage pre-treatment for adhesive bonding the manufacturing integration increases and the number of production steps reduces. Besides, the adhesive bonding can imply a high preparatory expenditure, several minutes curing as well as several joining jigs.

3 INVESTIGATION OF THE PHOTONIC JOINING ZONE TREATMENT

Laser treatment is already used for micro structuring as an adhesive bonding pre-treatment [6], for shafting (stepwise removal of fibers and matrix) for the preparation of FRP repair [7], as well as for exposing and following laser transmission welding of dissimilar types of FRP [5].

In the OPTO-Light process, beside the selective material removal and fiber exposing the joining zone is locally heated by the 3d laser processing head. So the viscosity of the thermoplastic material in the injection molding step is reduced and the microform closure is improved additionally. The interaction of the laser radiation with the treated material highly depends on the used laser source [8]. A short pulse laser was chosen because of its potential for high exposing rates per costs. For the investigations of the laser treatment process, the carbon fiber-reinforced thermoset of the company SGL, Wiesbaden, named Sigratex CE 8201-200-45 (A) was used. This 2 mm laminate is built up by a twill fabric (200 g/m², 3k) and epoxy resin (201).

The application of energy into the surface was changed by variation of the laser beam feed speed and the resulting surface morphology was investigated. Figure 3 shows the different fiber structures caused by the increase of the laser beam feed speed from 750 mm/s to 3.000 mm/s. With reduced energy input, the exposing depth and the fiber bracing decreases. Furthermore the amount of the remaining resin increases because of the textile specific fiber undulation.

Figure 3: Variation of the energy input for different fiber exposing results
(laser beam feed speed: left 750 mm/s, right 3,000 mm/s)

To investigate the influence of the twill fabric, a second laminate with the same fiber volume content and epoxy resin, SGL Sigratex CE 8201-245-45 (B), 245 g/m², 3k, was used. Figure 4 shows an increasing remaining amount of resin with the specific number of fiber undulation.

Figure 4: Remaining amount of resin, depending on the fiber undulation
(laser beam feed speed: 1,500 mm/s)

The analysis of the investigation backs the need for a feedback control of the pulsed laser process, to reach a homogeneous exposing quality, even by varying the fiber architecture and resin thickness of the top layer. Currently, a process control isn't commercially available for the scanner-based laser treatment of FRP with pulsed laser beam neither by means of a pyrometer nor by means of an on-line surface detection. Therefore, such a technology will be developed within "OPTO-Light".

Figure 5 illustrates the level of matrix sublimation between the carbon fibers (SGL Sigratex CE 8201-200-45 (A), laser beam feed speed: 1,500 mm/s), which is the basis for the subsequent microform closure, generated in the injection molding process. Significant damages of the fibers are not visible.

Figure 5: SEM analysis of the level of matrix sublimation as the basis for microform closures

The derivation of an optimum morphology of the joining zone surface is possible only by including the subsequent back-molding of fiber-reinforced thermoplastic molding compounds.

4 INVESTIGATION OF THE OPTO-LIGHT PROCESS

The focus of the process-related investigation is to analyze the effect of process parameters on the component quality. This includes also the detection of relations between material properties, single process parameters and the machinery. For a detailed understanding of the laser treatment process and the influence on the following plastic processing, tensile shear test specimen were produced and the shear strength of the back-molded joining is determined. The used specimen was designed according to DIN EN ISO 527-2 with an overlapping of 12.5 mm and 8 mm, orientated to DIN EN 1465:2009 (see figures 6 and 7).

Figure 6: Front: Thermoset CFRP part with exposed fiber structure at the joining zone (SGL Sigratex CE 8201-200-45 (A))

Back: Hybrid specimen with back-molded short glass fiber-reinforced thermoplast (LANXESS Durethan BKV 30)

With the materials of the first investigation (thermoset: CFRP twill fabric SGL Sigratex CE 8201-200-45 (A) and CE 8201-245-45 (B); thermoplast: PA6-GF LANXESS Durethan BKV 30), the parameter variation tests result in a maximum shear strength of 14,2 MPa, without process optimization. The results show a maximum scattering of 1 MPa, so the single process steps may be considered as repeatable. Main influences on the quality of the joining, identified in the first investigation are the exposed architecture of the fabric (difference between SGL (A) and SGL (B) material, see figure 4), the parameter laser beam feed speed and the holding pressure of the back-molding process (also figures 8 and 9). [9]

Due to the multi-axial stress condition of the joining zone of the specimen (additional bending moment and tension peaks), the measuring values have to be seen as relative characteristic values. The reached shear strength can be classified in the same field, compared to back-molded specimens, made of a pair of similar fiber-reinforced thermoplastic materials [10]. With a dissimilar thermoplastic material combination of PA6-GF30 (injection molded) and PA66-CF (laser treated insert) the test resulted in a shear strength of 11,2 MPa [9].

On the basis of these results, further investigations of the influences of the laser treatment process, the resin material and the injection molding process were carried out. For these investigations, the thermoset CFRP component was manufactured by using state of the art thermoset epoxy resins and carbon fibers (unidirectional non-crimp fabric) of the project partner BMW and the Gap Impregnation machinery, developed at the Institute of Plastics Processing (IKV) at RWTH Aachen University. Figure 7 illustrates the test specimen.

Figure 7: Injection molded tensile shear test specimen, according to DIN EN ISO 527-2

The results of the injection molding process are illustrated in figure 8, in relation to the process center point (compound temperature: 275°C, mold temperature: 90°C, injection speed: 75 cm³/s, holding pressure: 250 bar). Injection speed, thermoset insert temperature and melt temperature have a positive effect on the shear strength, while the mold temperature shows a certain process optimum in this test series.

Figure 8: Results of variation of injection molding process parameters

As assumed, the influence of higher injection pressures, due to higher injection speeds is positive, but in this test series not significant because of the overlap of varies effects on the compound during the injection in the used mold and gate system. The positive influence of lower viscosities during the

impregnation of the fibers may be seen by the varied process temperatures. The resulted lower shear strength of the high mold temperatures may be caused by a too short cooling time for this mold temperature. The holding pressure effect is seen as not significant in this test series and needs further investigations.

Besides the influences of the injection process, the laser treatment process was investigated regarding the laser beam feed speed and the epoxy resin material system. The three tested material systems are high reactive epoxies with different reaction characteristics, low viscosities (e.g. ~1 min, 115°C, < 200 mPas) and short curing cycles (e.g. 2 min, 115°C) of the project partner BMW. The results are shown in figure 9. Independent of the material system, the laser beam feed speed shows a local optimum between 4,000 – 8,000 mm/s (puls-to-puls distance 57 - 114 µm) in the joining quality. This may be seen as the optimum energy input, relatively to exposing depth, fiber bracing and potential fiber surface damages. By comparison, only material 1 shows up a maximum at 20,000 mm/s with higher scattering, which has to be investigated in further tests. The reached maximum shear strength of every material is above 13 MPa and overall 14.95 MPa.

Figure 9: Results of variation of injection molding process parameters

By SEM-photographs, the correlation of measured shear strength and the quality of the impregnation can be shown. So future process investigations to optimize the component strength will be about the influences of form-fit, force-fit and adhesive bonding mechanism between dissimilar joining partners (see figure 10). Additionally, the determination of characteristic values of the bonding, based on alternative developed specimen geometry, for torsion and pull up tests, of the Institute of Plastics Processing (IKV) of RWTH Aachen University will be intended [11].

Figure 10: SEM-micrograph of the joining cross section, in injection direction

9 CONCLUSIONS

It was shown, that the procedure of the project "OPTO-Light" is applicable to intrinsic joining of thermoset and thermoplastic FRP in principle. With the used thermoset materials (continuous carbon fiber-reinforced epoxies) and the short fiber-reinforced thermoplastic material (PA6-GF30), tensile shear strengths of up to 14.95 MPa were measured, without parameter optimization. Furthermore, the influences of the process parameters of the laser treatment process (local fiber exposing by matrix sublimation) and the injection molding process were identified. The results of the laser process show that pulsed laser sources with industrial power specifications are suitable for the efficient treatment of different carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy resin systems. The variation of the laser beam feed speed resulted in a shear strength optimum due to the application of energy. Regarding the requirement to achieve a defined joining surface characteristic and bonding, independent of manufacturing tolerances and materials, the investigation indicates the need of a controlled laser treatment process including appropriate sensor technology for the industrial use of the laser treatment technology. The identified influences of single parameters of the injection process refer to a realization of further process optimization for increasing shear strengths.

Future investigations with the aim of higher shear strength are focused on the characterization of an optimized laser treated surface, the analysis of correlations between material characteristics (e.g. fiber orientations, fiber length, resin layer thickness), laser control (e.g. pulse energy, puls-to-puls distance) and the interlinked process steps. With the ongoing development of the integrative process technology and implementation in a single integrative production cell at AZL of RWTH Aachen University, the novel material combination of thermoset continuous FRP and thermoplastic FRP may be realized in the industrial field.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank the German Ministry of Education and Research, BMBF for the support of the research activities within the project "OPTO-Light" (funding ref. no. 13N12696). Special thanks goes to the project partners and all AZL partner institutes of RWTH Aachen University for the support and successful cooperation. Further we thank the LANXESS Deutschland GmbH for the provided material.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Hoffschlag, *Forschungsbedarf zum Fügen von Kunststoffen im Leichtbau und im Bereich der erneuerbaren Energien*, DVS-Berichte, Vol. 294, DVS Media GmbH, Düsseldorf, 2012.
- [2] P. Amend, T. Frick, M. Schmidt, Experimental Studies on Laser-based Hot-melt Bonding of thermosetting Composites and Thermoplastics, *Proceedings of the Laser in manufacturing Conference 2011*, Physics Procedia 12, Elsevier B.V., 2011, p. 166-173.
- [3] R.C. Don, S.H. McKnight, A. Wetzel, A. McIntire, J.W. Gillespie, Interpenetrating polymer networks of polyurethane and epoxy, *Journal of Materials Science*, 29, 1994, p. 5435-5440.
- [4] T. Beiss, *Vibrationsfügen von duroplastischen Faserverbunden mit abrasiven Schmelzklebstoffen auf Basis von Polyamid 6*, PhD-Thesis, Lehrstuhl fuer Kunststofftechnik, Erlangen, 2009.
- [5] P. Amend, T. Frick, B. Pillach, M. Schmidt, Laser-Based Hot-Melt Bonding of Thermosetting GFRP, *Laser Assisted Net Shape Engineering 7 (LANE 2012)*, Physics Procedia 39, Elsevier B.V., 2012, p. 147-153.
- [6] E. Buechter, M. Frauenhofer, S. Kreling, Laser zur Vorbehandlung beim Kleben von CFK. *MM Maschinenmarkt*, Sonderausgabe Juni 2011, Vogel Business Media, Wuerzburg, 2011.
- [7] F. Fischer, D. Kracht, U. Stute, F. Voelkermeyer, Laser-based approach for bonded repair of carbon fiber reinforced plastics, *Proceedings of the Laser in manufacturing Conference 2011*, Physics Procedia 12, Elsevier B.V., 2011, p. 537-542.

- [8] A. Wolynski, T. Herrmann, P. Mucha, H. Haloui, J. L'huillier, Laser ablation of CFRP using picosecond laser pulses at different wavelengths from UV to IR. LiM 2011, *Physics Procedia* 12, Elsevier B.V., 2011, p. 292-301.
- [9] M. Emonts, K. Fischer, R. Schares, S. Schmitt, Intrinsisches Fügen artungleicher, faserverstärkter Kunststoffe, befähigt durch photonische Prozesse, *Proceedings of the 7. Landshuter Leichtbau-Colloquium 2015 (Eds: O. Huber, M. Bicker, P. Patzelt)*, Landshut, Germany, February 25-26, 2015, Leichtbau-Cluster Hochschule Landshut, pp.145-155.
- [10] D. Drummer, J. Vittinghoff, G. Huelder, Montagespritzguss piezoaktiver Sandwichverbunde, *Journal of Plastics Technology*, 6, No. 4, 2010, Hanser Verlag.
- [11] C. Hopmann, J. van Haag, J. Schild, Bestimmung von Werkstoffkennwerten Probekörper zur Charakterisierung von Kunststoff-Metall-Hybridverbunden, *VDI Konstruktion*, 65, No. 11, 2013, p. IW8-IW10.